

Psychology in Crypto economics

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Hayk is a business expert and advisor in topics related to innovation, strategy, AI and blockchain to MNCs and startups globally. Hayk held senior roles of digital transformation and business turnaround around the world. He worked with and consulted SMEs and MNCs across Europe, Africa, and Asia.

Hayk is a partner at Vision Capital, ICO financial advisory in SEA, in addition to being Expert-in-Residence at SOSV, the biggest VC accelerator in the world and APAC partner at Prysm Group, the top blockchain economics and governance agency in the world.

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